

1 **A pluripotency associated transcript, HPAT5, is a component of the TE specification program in**
2 **hES cells.**

3 Shahan K. Mamoor, B.S., M.S., Ph.D cand.¹

4 ¹shahanmamoor@gmail.com

5 Chestnut Hill, MA USA 02467

6 East Islip, NY USA 11730

7 We measured total transcription in the inner cell mass (ICM) and the trophectoderm (TE) of the human
8 embryo to understand the mechanisms underlying TE commitment. We describe here discovery of HPAT5
9 as a lineage commitment factor or lineage commitment cooperating factor in embryonic stem cells of the
10 human embryo.

11 Citations

12 1. Durruthy-Durruthy, J., Sebastiano, V., Wossidlo, M., Cepeda, D., Cui, J., Grow, E.J., Davila, J.,
13 Mall, M., Wong, W.H., Wysocka, J. and Au, K.F., 2016. The primate-specific noncoding RNA HPAT5
14 regulates pluripotency during human preimplantation development and nuclear reprogramming. Nature
15 genetics, 48(1), pp.44-52.